

Windows 7 Stripping & Hardening, Part 3: Keep it Safe

Andrea Covello
Defense Department, scip AG
anco@scip.ch
https://www.scip.ch

Marc Ruef (Editor)
Research Department, scip AG
maru@scip.ch
https://www.scip.ch

Keywords: Basel, Browser, Firewall, Forensic, Framework, Hardening, Internet Explorer, Microsoft, Policy, Report

1. Preface

This paper was written in 2012 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20120906> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

- Part 1: OS Tools [1]
- Part 2: Hardening Procedures [2]
- Part 3: Keep it Safe

Coming to an end, after stripping and hardening, there is the need to keep the system secure and clean. This may be a difficult task to accomplish, because you may need to install and use new applications and of course the attack profiles changes over time. Therefore here some hints to help you out in this matter.

3. Apply Application Auditing

Microsoft just released a tool to the public, that was deployed for the internal application audit process, which was needed to be compliant to the *Microsoft Security Development Lifecycle* [3]. This tool name is *Attack Surface Analyzer* [4]

Basically this tool will create a snapshot of the system parameters in a known state: for example when you're done with the OS stripping/hardening. After the first run the tool will start a multiple scan procedure and *baseline* your system. The system state will be saved in a .cab file and will be used as a reference once you'll want to compare other systems state, for example after a software installation.

Below is a list of system areas changes & permissions settings that will be *baselined* (analyzed):

OS Area	Checked Items
System Information	Running Processes, Executables Memory Pages, Windows GUI, Kernel Objects, Impersonation Tokens, Kernel Objects
Service Information	Services, Drivers
ActiveX, DCOM, COM & File Registrations	Registered ActiveX Controls, Registered DCOM Servers, DCOM Default Permissions, Registered COM Controls, File Registration
Internet Explorer	Pluggable Protocol Handlers, Silent Elevation Entries, Preapproved Controls, Browser Helper Objects, Internet Explorer, IE Zones, IE Actions Policy
Network Information	Open/Used Ports (TCP/UDP), Named Pipes, RPC Endpoints, Network Shares, Network Interfaces
Firewall	Rules, Profiles, Service Restriction Rules & Authorized Application
System Environment, Users & Groups	PATH Entries, Accounts, Groups, Group Membership, Account Privileges

There is a lot to check and to be compared, so don't worry if it takes some time to execute all those tasks, just remember to stop all processes and programs not needed when you run the first *baseline* scan... Now just make the test:

Ensure you're have a clean OS state and start the Attack Surface Analyzer. The first time you have to select **scan** to generate the initial *baseline*

Now you'll see that several scanning processes are starting...

Once the scan is done you can start making change to your system installing a new application. When you're done, restart the Attack Surface scanner and select the comparing baseline created before (it will be selected by default)

The analysis will take a while before displaying the results

After the comparing process a report is created and displayed in the browser...

...dig into the detailed report for more information

You may wonder how much application and tools may change your system state and consequently the *attack surface* of your system!

Of course you can compare different *scan status* and (as you may already figure out) you can use this tool for forensics analysis, if you manage to have a clean *baseline* of the analyzing system.

The Attack Surface Analyzer comes free of charge and supports following OS:

- Windows Vista / Windows 7 / Windows 8
- Windows Server 2008 / 2008 R2 / 2012
- Windows Server Core 2008 / 2008 R2 / 2012

You can run the scan also in command mode to create the baseline files (.cab), but unfortunately you'll need to have the *.NET Framework 4* to compare the baselines and to generate the reports. At best you'll use a dedicated workstation for the reporting generation task.

4. Application Whitelisting

Another way to keep your system clean and safe is to provide a known list of application that may run on your machine, this approach is known as Whitelisting. As the words says, only application listed as known (and safe) are able to execute.

It really is a possibility to achieve a very secure operation state but it also need a long tuning session where you define and configure all application needed to run and its required executables. The Application Auditing explained above really helps in this task and is a prerequisite to accomplish successful Whitelisting.

Following are key points for Application Whitelisting:

- Executables integrity (the binary code has not changed since the auditing)
- Executables path integrity (knowing where the binary is)
- Executable permission profile (define what the binary code is able to do)

In Windows you'll use the *Group Policy Editor (GPO)* to define and enforce Application Whitelisting.

Figure: " class=

We just scratched the surface of the possibilities with Application Whitelisting, more on this item may be discussed in dedicated Lab article.

5. Summary

In this article we covered the security procedure on keeping a hardened system secure over time. Now this series has reached the end, but stay tuned for future labs articles.

6. External Links

- [1] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20120524>
- [2] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20120705>
- [3] <http://www.microsoft.com/security/sdl/default.aspx> title="SDL"
- [4] <http://blogs.msdn.com/b/sdl/archive/2012/08/02/attack-surface-analyzer-1-0-released.aspx>
- [5] [labs/images/anco_2012-09_07.png](#)
- [6] [labs/images/anco_2012-09_08.png](#)